

THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTER DURING LEARNING

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Abstract

Flora Lewis invites us to reason about the following sentence, "Learning another language is not only learning different words for the same things, but learning another way to think about things." (Flora Lewis)

Confirmed Processes: It has been confirmed that learning is the only life-long process that will never stop happening in one form or another, whatever path it takes to gain knowledge. Nowadays, where becoming a global citizen has become a necessity, the need to learn foreign languages arises. This process not only creates a passage-way for life, but opens doors along this path.

It has been confirmed that learning processes are contacts during which we receive, register, classify, reinforce, compare, reason, synthesize, accept, contradict, internalize sets of knowledge, execute cultivated behaviors, maintain attitudes, lobby, self-actualize within our socio-cultural environments and in foreign socio-cultural and linguistic environments.

It has been confirmed that there is a variety of learning. In order for the learning process to be effective, it is important to find the right methods to accomplish the learning. These techniques and methods are "investigated" from time to time to verify if they are still appropriate for the learning process or if there is a need to experiment with new methods.

Keywords: Linguistic operant system, unconscious language acquisition, language transfer errors, linguistic analogy errors, bilingual education.

Introduction

Learning is the only process in life that never ceases to happen in one way or another, whatever the path that leads to the acquisition of knowledge is. Nowadays, where becoming a global citizen has become a necessity, the need to learn foreign languages arises. This process not only creates a corridor for life, but opens doors along this path.

But what is the process of learning a foreign language? How does learning a foreign language happen? What are the ways of effective learning and what are the reasons that this process is so significant?

The learning process is the act of acquiring, reinforcing, modifying existing knowledge, values, skills, or synthesizing different types of information.

There are many types of learning. In order for the learning process to be effective, it is important to find the right methods for this approach. These techniques are investigated from time to time to verify if they are still appropriate for the learning process or if there is a need to experiment with new methods.

What is the learning process?

The process of learning a foreign language is the same as that of any other subject with the only difference being that it takes place outside the environment in which the foreign language is spoken. Often the only difference between the process of learning a foreign language is that between 'foreign language' and 'second language'. Second language is a term which means that this language is spoken as an official language in this country. A foreign language is one that is learned outside of any context of its use.

Studying a foreign language allows the individual to communicate effectively and creatively, as well as participate in real-life situations through which he

learns the culture and provides a meaningful approach to perspectives different from his own, enhances the ability to see connections between different countries while also promoting interdisciplinary perspectives and simultaneously gaining intercultural understandings.

Considering it from this point of view, language is the necessary tool for an effective communication between people, helping them not only to get to know other cultures, but also to better understand their own culture. The process of learning a foreign language provides the student with the opportunity to benefit from social and linguistic knowledge in order to know what to say, when to say it and where to say it (*Educational Project of Foreign Languages (2014)*).

Krashen's Theory: According to Krashen's monitoring theory, the process of learning a foreign language presents two hypotheses, according to which the individual has two operating systems to learn a foreign language: unconscious foreign language acquisition and conscious learning of foreign language.

In the first hypothesis, Krashen asserts that the process of acquiring a foreign language happens as naturally as the learning of the mother tongue by children. This necessarily requires practical communication of the language being learned, in which speakers should not be concerned so much with the form of expression, but with the accurate and clear conveyance of the message. Explicit learning of rigid grammatical rules is not so necessary in the acquisition of a foreign language (*Brown and Halton, 1970; Brown, Cazden, Bellugi, 1973*).

However, this does not mean that teachers or native speakers who care to teach cannot simplify the learning process by finding easier ways of expression

to aid in the learning process (*Snow and Ferguson, 1977*)).

In the second hypothesis, he claims that the conscious learning of a foreign language is also helped by the grammatical connections that students make while speaking. If in language acquisition they do not pay attention to strict grammatical rules, during the conscious learning process these rules play a very important role also in correct thinking. During this process, the individual progresses from simple learning to complex learning, unlike the first process (*Fanselow, 1977; Long, 1977*).

Following this logic, James Lantolf, a researcher who was also extensively involved in further expanding Vygotsky's theory¹ in foreign language learning, asserts that foreign language learners progress to higher levels of language proficiency when they collaborate and interact with speakers of the foreign language who possess it to a higher degree.

However, the learning process is very complex and continuous and as such requires comprehensive support of all actors in the field of education, so that it is comprehensive.

The role of the mother tongue in the process of learning a foreign language

The role of the mother tongue in the process of learning a foreign language has been widely discussed for many years, often being seen as a problem that hinders this process. For years it has been assumed that the mother tongue is the only source of syntactic errors of individuals learning a foreign language (*Lado, 1957*).

Subsequent empirical studies on the errors made during the foreign language learning process have led researchers to discover that these errors do not necessarily result from the interference of the native language, but are habitual among foreign language speakers who have different linguistic backgrounds (*Buteau, 1971*).

Mother tongue can be a hindering factor especially when: a student acquires new vocabulary, tries to remember previously learned vocabulary or when he tries to form more complex sentences or expressions.

Since the great reform at the end of the 19th century, the role of the mother tongue is one of the most discussed methodological problems. Currently, official guidelines in many countries recommend that planned learning be as monolingual as possible, relying on the mother tongue only when learning difficulties arise.

In this dispute, an agreement has been reached in favor of a type of monolingualism with minor concessions: 'There is no point in trying to suppress the mother tongue completely' (*Harmer, 2001: 132*). The mother tongue is generally considered a maneuver, which is used only in emergencies. Effective bilingual teaching techniques are a good one, not considered by schools. It often even seems that the so-called direct method, the use of monolinguals, is the new communicative approach and seems to have triumphed over all other methodologies.

Students' performance in foreign language acquisition is often marked by problems, which Pit Corder

(*'Error analysis and interlanguage', 1908*) classifies into three categories:

- a. Transferring errors
- b. Analogy errors
- c. Errors caused during learning

These mistakes generally come because all students are members of a community, therefore the mistakes are generally the same since the views on reality are the same.

However, there are also some positive aspects of the mother tongue, which help students learn foreign languages.

Foreign language learning generally begins in the third grade of primary education. The third grade student faces a new language, while the learning process is not unknown to him. Languages cooperate with each other and therefore the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by learning the mother tongue will help the student to understand the foreign language more easily. In a way, the phonetic system of the Albanian language can positively interfere with the pronunciation of foreign language phonemes.

As Pit Corder also says, the mother tongue gives us a language that is rich in hypotheses and can be used to learn a foreign language. Many of these hypotheses can be confirmed because languages have many things in common. Starting from this point of view, when learning a foreign language, the student does not discover everything to zero because most foreign languages have the same basic rules for ordering words in sentences or almost the same grammatical categories.

According to many linguists, being proficient in the mother tongue would be a help for students in the better acquisition of foreign languages. While the student has knowledge of the mother tongue, he is able to make the connection between the two languages.

"He who understands the grammar of one language is capable of understanding the grammar of another language in terms of grammatical rules. However, they fail to understand or speak a foreign language because of the varieties of words or different grammatical forms that differ from one language to another." Roger Bacon.

Do we struggle when we learn the mother tongue?

Of course not. This is a process that arises naturally: first with stuttering, then with word formations and up to the construction of sentences with correct grammar. Most people start speaking in their mother tongue at the age of 4 and above.

Learning a second language happens in the same way. We cannot claim to be advanced from the beginning as each stage requires not only an investment of time, but also depends on the exposure the individual has to the environment in which this language is spoken.

The mother tongue has a main function in learning a foreign language because it also increases self-confidence, especially when the second language occurs at a young age in children.

According to Carless (*2008:331*), mother tongue has both advantages and disadvantages. It can serve social and cognitive functions. The use of the mother

tongue is also related to the recognition of the national identity as long as it conveys the culture of the country giving positive feelings to the student. The mother tongue serves as a skeleton in learning a foreign language as many of the functions of words in sentences are transferred from it to the foreign language. According to him, the negative sides are related to supporting the student more than necessary in the native language while he is learning a foreign language. This mother tongue interference can often be harmful because the order of words in a sentence, for example, may not always be identical from one language to another. However, good students manage to translate from one language to another, taking into account the characteristics and linguistic functions of one language and another.

In conclusion, we can say that the mother tongue is multidimensional in learning a foreign language along with its positive and negative sides. It teaches the student to expand vocabulary and reading skills in a foreign language, but it interferes with speaking and writing in a foreign language.

Teaching a foreign language can be as difficult a process as learning it. For this reason, it should be considered as one of the most important factors during student learning. Finding efficient methods for improving foreign language learning with as little native language interference as possible is a must. It would be ridiculous to arbitrarily exclude the mother tongue as a tool for teaching a foreign language, however as long as it is not overused in the classroom environment it can have a positive didactic function.

How the learning process happens in children and adults

There are generally two ways that children learn a foreign language: simultaneously and sequentially (McLaughlin, 1995; Tabors, 2008).

Students who learn a foreign language simultaneously with their mother tongue are those children who are exposed to the mother tongue (in this case, the language of their parents) at home and are exposed to the language of the community in which they live through educational programs, which can do at school. Another case could be children, who have parents with different citizenships and who speak two languages to the children at home.

Up to a certain age children learn both languages with the same intensity and therefore do not prefer one language over another. This is because they build the same and equally strong language systems in their brains for both languages they hear. These separate systems allow children to learn two different languages without having a problem and without having one language interfere with the other. In fact, this path followed by these children, who are in some form bilingual, is also followed by children who have only one language as their mother tongue. After a certain age, for example 6 years, exposure to a third foreign language can influence these children to have preferences for a language over a language other than the one their parents speak. Therefore, it can often happen that most of the words or grammatical systems of a language can be

lost. Knowing this, parents should be careful and expose the child to the same amount of words in the second language that he is exposed to in the first language.

Children who are sequential learners are those who are introduced to a second foreign language in the school environment, as part of the curriculum of that country. Unlike children, who are bilingual students, the learning of these children can happen at any age and can also depend on external factors such as: the skill and motivation of the student.

For years it has been thought that learning a foreign language for children is useless. For this reason, many studies have been developed, which sought precisely to find more meaningful answers on this topic. Harvard University confirms the opposite of what has been claimed to date. Children learning a foreign language at an early age not only makes them more creative, but also develops their critical thinking and flexibility of thinking. This is also related to the fact that learning a foreign language is a cognitive activity more than a linguistic activity.

If we were to consider this statement from a biological point of view, it would be right to also mention the active function that children's brains take on during the learning process, since this activity includes memorizing vocabulary or grammar rules.

According to Dr. Pascual-Leone, the younger the student is when learning a foreign language, the higher the chances of correct pronunciation and imitation of the phonemes of a language.

At a young age, e.g. 3 years old, children have the opportunity to learn through the game process. Their learning becomes more fun and grammar formulas are given through informal speech as children's brains are less complex and more open to new processes and language functions. At this age, before children become aware of their speech they have more self-confidence and less awkwardness while speaking.

Children who grow up learning a foreign language makes them more empathetic towards others, teaches them to understand their own culture and respect the culture of others, and prepares them to take their place in a global society. Among other things, career opportunities increase for those who have more languages to offer.

If children manage to learn a foreign language at a young age in the same way they learn their mother tongue, could adults learn a foreign language like children?

In fact, no one has looked more closely at this question than linguist Stephan Krashen.

According to him, it is important to distinguish between learning a foreign language with traditional models: grammar, vocabulary, and acquiring a foreign language: creating real situations in the same way that young children learn their mother tongue. So foreign language acquisition, a must for adults, happens where action and practice happen.

How can adults acquire a foreign language? According to Krashen, these stages of learning are divided as follows:

1. *We acquire a foreign language when we begin to understand messages in that language:*

According to Krashen, this is called comprehensible input and is about the exposure of comprehensible listening and reading materials. He also insists that in adults the emphasis should be on the interaction rather than form. If an adult says 'There are fishes in the lake' the correction should be 'Right, there is fish in the lake' without having to correct the grammar. (Krashen, 1983)

2. *The period of silence*

It was mentioned above that this period also happens with children during the process of learning a foreign language. Even adults can have their own problem period, regardless of the fact that exposure to a foreign language can also happen outside of the classroom. If the student does not participate actively during class discussions, it does not mean that he is not paying attention. It may simply be a signal that he is acquiring the foreign language unconsciously (Krashen, 1983).

3. *Anxiety is a student's worst enemy*

The article also mentions the reason that children learn foreign languages better because of the lack of fear and embarrassment in speaking. The opposite happens to adults during the learning process. This best reminds us of Krashen's most famous point of view: the emotional filter. During the process of learning a foreign language, its acquisition drops significantly if the student is under stress. For adults, the classroom can be an environment that causes anxiety when acquiring comprehensible input.

One of the advantages that children have over adults when learning a foreign language is that children do not speak the language for the purpose of language acquisition. They talk and learn it as a fun activity unlike adults, who are forced to be perfectionists.

In conclusion, we can say that learning a foreign language is a process that requires time and dedication, whether the student is a child or an adult. The important thing is that the process happens naturally and is fun.

What are the barriers that students encounter in learning a foreign language and what are some effective methods that would help them learn a foreign language?

The question of why some students "grab" a foreign language faster compared to others has worried researchers and teachers, making the discussed topic an object of study to reach a common solution to help students.

Nowadays, studying a foreign language at school is a requirement of a country's educational programs, so students must be able to speak at least one foreign language in addition to their mother tongue.

The students who have more difficulties in learning a foreign language are precisely those who have also had difficulties in acquiring the reading of their mother tongue at a young age.

We often hear that in order to acquire a foreign language, we must live in the country where the foreign

language is spoken. There are some studies that affirm it, however there are many others that also affirm that the classroom environment can help students learn a foreign language. The classroom can be a barrier to learning if the use of the foreign language is limited. At the same time it can be useful if it is the main source of understandable data (Krashen, 1982).

Krashen also lists the obstacles that are encountered during the time when the foreign language is taught in the classroom. It can never be claimed that it would be spoken with the same fluency if it were acquired in the countries where the foreign language is spoken. Learning in an informal environment may transmit inaccurate inputs to the student, but the intensity with which the foreign language is conveyed during a day in a foreign country is the same as the lessons developed during a week at school. The classroom environment tries to create learning situations similar to those of the real world, but which again may not be as fruitful and as real as those in the natural environment.

The classroom will never be able to overcome their own barriers to learning a foreign language, however its purpose is not to be a substitute for the outside environment, but to bring students to the point where they can understand the necessary information. When they are out of class making the student competent in speaking and conveying information.

Sometimes these difficulties also extend to the potential and motivation of students within the classroom. Students may also have difficulties in the syntax and morphology of their native language, so it is often a double challenge for the teacher to simplify the foreign language for the student.

Nowadays, where the possibilities of experimenting with teaching methods are numerous, the teacher can lobby to make the lesson interactive, fun and at the same time very effective.

First stage: Analysis of students who are learning a foreign language:

- a. Are they active or passive learners?
- b. Do they use prior linguistic knowledge or not?
- c. Do they make or not the connection or analogy of the grammatical rules of the mother tongue with the foreign language?
- d. Are they confident when they try to express themselves in a foreign language?

These important questions are raised according to many researchers Hosenfeld, Stern, Todesco when designing teaching strategies by the teacher. It is often difficult to adapt to the individual needs of students in a lesson, however identifying the problems can be the first step towards an efficient solution.

Second stage: Creating a student-centered lesson in order to increase their responsibility as students

A student-centered lesson creates and motivates the student not only in the learning process, but also to increase his responsibility, to ask questions, to be more social, to become a more active thinker.

Third phase: To increase the mother's motivation during the process of learning a foreign language.

This stage is one of the most important if we are talking about learning a foreign language. This is made

difficult not only because learning in general is a difficult process, but especially when it happens in a language that is not the mother tongue.

A cooperation between the teacher and the student to set clear goals on the reasons why we should acquire a foreign language would increase their motivation to continue learning this foreign language. The goals can be long-term or short-term, however it is extremely important that they are realized by the students and the teacher. If a long-term goal would be to publish a book in a foreign language by the end of the year itself, a short-term goal would be, for example, to publish a novel by the end of the week.

Fourth stage: Integrating theory with practice during the learning process

This phase is one of the most important as it allows the teacher to understand how the learning process has taken place as it integrates theory, eg giving instructions, by practice, eg putting the given instructions to work.

This is also the final stage, Krashen's theory on foreign language acquisition is put into practice: grammar learning, monitoring, acquisition, motivation of the student.

In conclusion, we can say that communicating with students and creating a comfortable and fun environment can make the learning process not only easier,

but also more productive. What teachers should try to do is to transform the classroom and teaching methods into their tool so that they serve the purpose.

Learning is a treasure that follows you everywhere. Why not giving more importance to the process of learning foreign languages? Language will always remain the map that leads you to culture. It tells you where people come from and where they are going. So that as an important part of the individual it would be a common good for a common purpose of improvement and further development of such processes.

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